

Reactivity of sulfite towards tris(pyridine-2-carboxylato)-manganese(III) in picolinate-picolinic acid buffer

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The kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of sulfite to sulfate by tris(pyridine-2-carboxylato)manganese(III) in Na(pic)-picH (where, Na(pic) = sodium salt of picolinic acid, picH = picolinic acid) buffer has been studied in the pH range 5.22–6.10. The rate of the reaction increases with increasing [substrate] but with decreasing acidity. A mechanism consistent with experimental observation has been proposed and the activation parameters for the rate-determining step evaluated.

The oxidation of SO₂ in aqueous and gaseous phases have received considerable attention and the environmental aspects of these reactions have also been reported¹. The kinetics of the oxidation of sulfite solutions by various oxidants have been reviewed². While the oxidation of sulfite by some oxidants³ produce dithionate in addition to sulfate, others⁴ yield only sulfate as the product. The present report is an investigation into the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation of SO₂ by tris(pyridine-2-carboxylato)manganese(III)⁵ in Na(pic)-picH buffer in the pH range 5.22–6.10.

Results and Discussion

The reactions were studied at varying initial concentrations of Mn^{III} in the range (4.0–8.0) × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³, but at constant [sulfite], pH and temperature of 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, 5.63 and 288 K, respectively. The average pseudo-first order rate constant (*k*_{obs}) was found to be (1.72 ± 0.4) × 10⁻³ s⁻¹. This indicates that the reaction is first order with respect to [Mn^{III}]. The pseudo-first order rate constants were also determined at different substrate concentrations (0.2–1.2) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ but at constant [Mn^{III}] and pH of 4.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³ and 5.63, respectively. The values of *k*_{obs} at different sulfite concentrations and at four different

temperatures are recorded in Table 1. The plots of *k*_{obs} vs [sulfite] are linear and passing through the origin. The quotients *k*₂ = *k*_{obs}/[sulfite] are 1.71, 2.43, 3.20 and 4.12 dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ at the temperatures 288, 293, 298 and 303 K, respectively.

The effect of changing [H⁺] on *k*_{obs} was also studied in the pH range 5.22–6.10 and at [Mn^{III}] and [sulfite] of 5.0 × 10⁻⁵ and 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, respectively. Increasing [H⁺] was found to retard the reaction rate and a plot of 1/*k*₂ vs [H⁺] (Fig. 1) gave straight-lines with positive intercepts on the ordinate at different temperatures. No attempt has been

Fig. 1. Plots of 1/*k*₂ vs [H⁺] at different temperatures; [Mn^{III}] = 5.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³, [sulfite] = 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³.

Table 1. Effect of variation of [sulfite] on the pseudo-first order rate constants at different temperatures

[Mn^{III}] = 5.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³, pH = 5.63

[Sulfite]	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> _{obs} (s ⁻¹)			
	288	293	298	303 K
10 ³ mol dm ⁻³				
0.2	3.42	4.86	6.41	8.53
0.4	6.75	9.53	12.8	17.0
0.5	8.55	12.2	15.9	21.3
0.6	10.2	14.5	19.4	25.4
0.8	13.6	19.4	25.5	33.6
1.0	17.2	24.5	32.0	42.5
1.2	20.8	29.2	38.1	50.4

made to keep the ionic strength fixed, since ionic strengths (varied by the addition of NaClO₄) do not have any effect on k_{obs} .

The values of K_a , the dissociation constant of HSO₃⁻ were calculated from the slopes of the plots of $1/k_2$ vs $[H^+]$ and found to be 1.50×10^{-7} , 1.65×10^{-7} , 1.80×10^{-7} and 1.91×10^{-7} at 288, 293, 298 and 303 K, respectively. The values of K_a are of the same order as reported earlier⁶ (1.02×10^{-7}) for the dissociation of HSO₃⁻. The change of K_a with temperature is not significant which is in keeping with the trends reported for weak acids⁷. From the intercepts of the plots of $1/k_2$ vs $[H^+]$, the values for the rate constant k for the slowest step of the reaction were calculated to be 28.6, 36.4, 44.4 and 57.1 dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ at 288, 293, 298 and 303 K, respectively. The enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) was calculated from the slope of the plot of $\log(k/T)$ vs $1/T$, whereas the entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) was calculated using Eyring equation. The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are 30 ± 4 kJ mol⁻¹ and -110 ± 13 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹, respectively.

Sulfurous acid does not exist in the free state nor does it exist in aqueous solution. It rather exists as SO₃²⁻ and HSO₃⁻ in aqueous medium. The ionic equilibria for sulfurous acid are as follows⁸:

The values of K_1 and K_2 are 1.54×10^{-2} and 1.02×10^{-7} , respectively, at 291 K⁶. Since the oxidation of sulfite was investigated in the pH range 5.22–6.01 and H⁺ ion inhibits the reaction rate, it is suggested that the unprotonated (SO₃²⁻) rather than the protonated (HSO₃⁻) species reacts mainly with the oxidant. The SO₃²⁻ ion formed by the dissociation of HSO₃⁻ reacts with the Mn^{III} complex to give the radical SO₃^{•-} and [Mn^{II}(C₅H₄NCO₂)₃]⁻. The Mn^{II} complex, in presence of water, is likely to form the more stable aquated form [Mn^{II}(C₅H₄NCO₂)₂(H₂O)₂], with the liberation of a picolinate ion. The formation of Mn^{II} was confirmed by the appearance of a typical six-line EPR spectrum. The SO₃^{•-} radical so formed undergoes further one-electron oxidation by another [Mn^{III}(C₅H₄NCO₂)₃] molecule to give SO₃ which is subsequently converted to SO₄²⁻ as shown in step (7) of Scheme 1. The intervention of a free radical intermediate was confirmed by the formation of polymerized products on addition of vinyl products to the reaction mixture.

Table 2. Stoichiometric results on the oxidation of sulfite by Mn^{III}

Initial 10 ³ [Mn ^{III}] mol dm ⁻³	Initial 10 ³ [sulfite] mol dm ⁻³	Final 10 ³ [Mn ^{III}] mol dm ⁻³	Final 10 ³ [sulfite] mol dm ⁻³	$\frac{\Delta[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]}{\Delta[\text{sulfite}]}$
1.85	0.35	1.16	0.00	1.98
2.50	0.25	2.00	0.00	2.01
0.40	2.00	0.00	1.79	1.93
0.50	5.00	0.00	4.74	1.89

followed by step (5),

Scheme 1

The rate expression may be deduced as follows:

$$-\frac{d[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]}{dt} = k [\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}][\text{SO}_3^{2-}] \quad (8)$$

$$\text{and } K_a = \frac{[\text{SO}_3^{2-}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{HSO}_3^-]} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{or, } -\frac{d[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]}{dt} = k [\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}] \frac{K_a}{K_a + [\text{H}^+]} [\text{HSO}_3^-] \quad (10)$$

Hence,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k K_a}{K_a + [\text{H}^+]} [\text{HSO}_3^-],$$

$$\text{where } k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{1}{[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]} \frac{d[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]}{dt} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{and } k_2 = \frac{k K_a}{K_a + [\text{H}^+]} \text{ where, } k_2 = k_{\text{obs}} / [\text{HSO}_3^-] \quad (12)$$

Rearranging eqn. (12), we have,

$$\frac{1}{k_2} = \frac{1}{k} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k K_a} \quad (13)$$

The plot of $1/k_2$ vs $[H^+]$ which makes an intercept on the y-axis is in conformity with the experimental observations.

Experimental

The complex tris(pyridine-2-carboxylato)manganese(III) was prepared and estimated as mentioned earlier⁷. Na₂SO₃ (J. T. Baker) and picolinic acid (Lancaster) were used. The sodium sulfite solution was standardised by using an excess of I₃ followed by back-titration with standard thiosulfate. The sulfite solutions were stored in the dark and used under subdued lighting condition usually within 5–6 h of preparation. The Na(pic)-picH buffer was prepared by mixing picolinic acid with its sodium salt in calculated amounts.

Kinetic measurements: The kinetic studies were carried out on a Systronics 166 spectrophotometer at 350 nm under pseudo-first order conditions, keeping the concentrations of the substrate in large excess over that of the oxidant. Freshly prepared sulfite solutions were used in kinetic measurements. Requisite volumes of the reactants were mixed and

the mixture was immediately transferred to a cell of path-length 1 cm. The cell compartment of the spectrophotometer was kept at constant temperature. Other reactants and products were nearly transparent at this wavelength. The rate of decrease of Mn^{III} was followed for at least two half-lives. Pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated from $\log A$ ($A = \text{absorbance}$) vs 'time' plots. The maximum error in the measurement of rate constant was 5% depending upon the experimental conditions.

Product analysis : the stoichiometry of the reaction was studied under two different experimental conditions. In the first set, $[Mn^{III}]$ was taken in excess over [sulfite]. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 1 h after which the excess of Mn^{III} estimated⁷. In the second set, [sulfite] was taken in excess over $[Mn^{III}]$. After completion of the reaction, the excess sulfite was estimated as mentioned above. The results of the two experiments are shown in Table 2. An average of different experiments indicates that the number of moles of Mn^{III} consumed per mole of sulfite is 1.95 ± 0.06 as shown below.

Dithionate was tested to be absent in the product mixture. Moreover, the observed stoichiometry rules out the formation of dithionate. The fact that picolinic acid is generated during the reaction was confirmed by the following test⁹. 2–3 drops of the reaction mixture containing the substrate and oxidant were mixed with a drop of a solution of $FeSO_4 \cdot (NH_4)_2SO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$ (1 g) and KF (0.5 g) in 0.1 N AcOH (100 ml) to give a light yellow colouration stable to acetic acid and other mineral acids. The formation of picolinate ion as one of the reaction products was further confirmed by the increase in absorbance with increase in Mn^{III} concentration, i.e. with increase in the amount of picolinate released¹⁰.

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